

THE RESULTS OF MICROPALAEONTOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF THE LATE MEOTIAN - EARLY PONTIAN DEPOSITS OF THE BLACK SEA REGION

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Abstract. The results of microfaunistical and palynological analysis of the Late Meotian - Early Pontian deposits of Eastern part of the Black Sea region are presented in the work. The data on the mollusks fauna studied from the same deposits were also used.

The microfaunistical analysis

In the Black Sea region the Lower Pontian is divided into two horizons – Eupatorian and Odessian. Eupatorian layers were established by Davitashvili (1933, 1937) on territory of Crimea, near the town Eupatoria. They contain the impoverished assemblages of brackish mollusks of the genera Eupatoria, Dreissena, Congeria, Prosodacna and others.

In the Eastern part of the Black Sea region the Eupatorian horizon first was established in outcrop on river Atapi (the left tributary of r. Duabi, between the villages Chlou and Tkina). Here are exposed deposits of Meotian on which the whole Pontian is conformably bedded (Taktakishvili, 1985). The following layers are exposed beginning from the bottom of the section:

1. Stratified, bluish-gray clays, which are changed by sandstones. The mollusks are represented mainly by brackish species: *Congeria novorossica* (Sinz.), *C. panticapaea* Andrus., *Theodoxus stephanescui* (Font.), *Caspihydrobia starabogatovi* L. I., *C. tamanensis* L. I., *Turricaspia brusinae* (Andrus.), *Sphaeronassa mutabilis andrusovi* Dav. By opinion of Badzoshvili (1986) this is the impoverished part of Early Meotian assemblage in which the mediterranean species are mainly preserved. Most of them are widely distributed in the Meotian deposits of Eastern Paratethys.

The Upper Meotian assemblage of foraminifers is represented by following species: *Quinqueloculina seminulum maeotica* Gerke, *Cycloforina gracilis* Karrer, *Sinuloculina* ex. gr. *consobrina* (d'Orb.), *Miliolinella* ex. gr. *circularis* (Born.), *Elphidium macellum maeotica* Gerke, *E. feodorovi* Bogd., *Ammonia becarii* (L.). The species, similar to mediterranean stenobiontic forms were not seen.

The assemblage of ostracods is composed from the following species: *Leptocythere maeotica* (Livent.), *L. scabruda* Suzin, *L. sulakensis* Suzin, *Cyprideis littoralis* (Brady), *C. punctillata* Brady, *Loxoconcha eichwaldi* Livent., *Caspiocypris candida* (Livent.), *Candona propria* Popch., *Caspiolla balkanica* (Zal.).

2. Bluish-gray sandy clays, with interlayers of yellow sandstones (40-50 cm) and lens with coquina, in which are determined: *Congeria novorossica* (Sinz.), *C. panticapaea* Andrus., *Prosodacna littoralis* (Eichw.), *Lythoglyphus* (?) sp. Thickness of layer 4 m.

3. Yellowish-gray sandy coquina, composed mainly from *Prosodacna littoralis* (Eichw.). Except this species are presented: *Congeria novorossica* (Sinz.), *C. panticapaea* Andrus., *C. navicula* Andrus., *Hydrobia* sp., *Neritina* sp., *Micromelania* sp. Thickness of layer is 10m.

In the layers 2 and 3 the following foraminifers were seen: *Quinqueloculina seminulum maeotica* Gerke, *Elphidium macellum maeotica* Gerke, *E. ex gr. pontica* Dolgopolskaya et Pauli, *Porosononion ex gr. subgranosus* (Egger), *Ammonia beccarii* (L.). The assemblage of ostracods is richer than in layer 1 and is composed from the following forms: *Caspiolla acronasuta* (Livent.), *Caspiolla venusta* (Zal.), *Caspiocypris labiata* (Zal.), *Candona* sp., *Cypria* sp., *C. tocorjescui* Hanganu, *Pontoniella accuminata* (Zal.), *P. loczyi* (Zal.), *Cyprideis torosa* Jones, *C. punctilata pliocenica* Rosjeva, *Leptocythere goitensis* (Suz.), *L. crebra* (Suz.), *L. ex gr. gutata* Suz., *L. collativa* Suz., *L. praebacuana* Livent., *L. pontica* Suz., *L. microlata* (Livent.), *Loxoconcha eichwaldi* Livent., *L. ex gr. temperata* Olteanu.

4. Bluish-gray sandy clay, with mollusks fauna: *Dreissena* sp., *Pontalmyra* (?)sp., *Pseudocatillus pseudocatillus* (Barb), *Prosodacna littoralis* (Eichw.), *Parvivenus widhalmi* Sinz., *Abra tellinoides* (Sinz.), *Lythoglyphus* (?) sp. Thickness of layer is 20m.

5. Bluish-gray clay, here and there sandy, with *Paradacna abichi* (R. Hoern.). In clays are also seen: *Congeria novorossica* (Sinz.), *Prosodacna littoralis* (Eichw.) and *Hydrobia* sp. Nearly on 15 m from base is located a small (0,4-0,5 m) intercalation of sandy clay with *Dreissena tenuissima* Andrus., *Pseudocatillus pseudocatillus* (Barb.), *Prosodacna littoralis* (Eichw.), *Parvivenus widhalmi* (Sinz.), *Hydrobia* sp., *Neritina* sp. The upper part of layer (20-25m) contains macroremains of plants. Thickness of layer is nearly 50m.

The layers 4 and 5 contain single foraminifers: *Quinqueloculina seminulum maeotica* Gerke and *Ammonia beccarii* (L.). Among ostracods are presented *Pontoniella accuminata* (Zal.), *P. loczyi* (Zal.), *Bakunella dorsoacuata* (Zal.), *Cypria tocorjescui* Hanganu, *Leptocythere andrussovii* Livent., *L. multituberculata* Livent., *L. praebacuina* Livent., *L. bosqueti* Livent., *L. cellula* Livent., *Pontoleberis pontica* Stanc., *Loxoconcha djaffarovi* Schneid., *Xestoleberis* sp.

By data of fauna in Atapi outcrop the deposits of Upper Meotian (layer 1) and Lower Pontian (layers 2-5) are presented. The layers 2 and 3 belong to Eupatorian and the layers 4, 5 to Odessian horizon.

By data of macrofauna the deposits of Eupatorian are characterized by impoverished assemblage of brackish mollusks. According to the data of Ebersin (1949) in the Black Sea-Caspian region the representatives of the genera Eupatoria, *Dreissena*, *Prosodacna*, *Monodacna* first appeared in Eupatorian. But more important is the fact of origin of several *Prosodacna* from the group "littoralis" on one and the same stratigraphical level. In Pliocene the expansion of brackish *Cardiidae* in basins of Ponto-Caspian region began by these forms.

As for microfauna in Meotian the predominate fossils are foraminifers. The ostracods are represented by single tests. The picture is changed in Eupatorian, in which deposits the abundance and specific variety of ostracods are increased. The assemblage has a mixed Meotian - Pontian composition, the genera *Pontoniella* and *Bakunella* are appeared here for the first time. The genera *Leptocythere* and *Loxoconcha* are represented by numerous species. The number of foraminifers and their specific composition is small. The assemblage composed from euryhaline species, which morphologically differ from taxa widely distributed in the Late Meotian. So, it is possible to say, that in Eupatorian the both assemblages are of mixed Meotian-Pontian composition.

In Odessian time (Lower Pontian) from the several basins of Paratethys into Rionian Bay, besides the species of genera *Pontoniella* and *Bakunella*, the representatives of genera *Caspiocypris*, *Lineocypris*, some *Leptocythere*, *Loxoconcha djaffarovi* Schneid, and *Cytherura perata* Schneider also penetrated. The Meotian relicts disappeared fully, but the common assemblage of ostracods became richer (Imnadze, 1974; Djanelize et al., 1985).

The ecological conditions of desalted Odessian Sea were fatal for foraminifers and in deposits of the

Odessian horizon they are represented by single *Quinqueloculina seminulum maeotica* and *Ammonia beccarii*.

In Western Georgia the second outcrop of Eupatorian horizon is situated in vicinity of village Bia. The following layers are exposed here:

1. Gray-bluish sandy clays with *Congeria subnovorossica* Osaul, *Hydrobia* sp., *Congeria panticcapaea* Andrus., *Abra tellinoides* Siniz., *Nassa* sp., *Cyprideis littoralis* Brady. On basis of this fauna the age of deposits is dated as Upper Meotian (Chelidze, 1971,1974; Popkhadze , 1974).

2. Yellowish-gray sandstone without mollusks. The foraminifers are represented by *Ammonia beccarii* (L.), *Porosonion* sp., *Elphidium* ex gr. *macellum* (F.et M.), *Nonion* ex gr. *bogdanowiczi* Volosh. and ostracods by *Caspiolla acronasuta* (Livent.), *Caspiocypris labiata* (Zal.), *Bakunella dorsoarcurata* (Zal.), *Pontoniella acumina-ta* (Zal.), *P. loszyi* (Zal.), *Hemicythera marinescui* Olteanu, *Urocytheris (Drobetaella)* ex gr. *mirabilis* Olteanu, *Cyprideis littoralis* (Brady). Thickness of layer 10-15m.

3. Grey-bluish clays with badly preserved mollusks. Thickness of layer 3m.

The mixed character of microfaunistical assemblage, the presence of Upper Meotian species side by side with species typical for Pontian and the presence of foraminifers peculiar for brackish basins of the Late Meo-tian allows to date the layer 2 of Bia outcrop as Eupatorian (Vekua 1979).

The layer 3 contains the microfaunistical assemblage, in which the foraminifers and Meotian species of ostracods are absent. In whole the assemblage is poor and monotonous, without forms typical for the Middle Pontian, which are represented in uppermost part of outcrop together with mollusk fauna. Accordingly, the age of the layer 3 is determined as Odessian.

The data about the microfauna of the Upper Meotian and Lower Pontian were used by Suladze (1984) for ecosystemic analysis of sedimentation basin of Eupatorian deposits. In the section near town Eupatoria two assemblages of foraminifers and ostracods of different age were established.

In lower part of outcrop foraminifers are represented by the following species: *Quinqueloculina seminu-lum maeotica* Gerke, *Cycloforina* aff. *gracilis* (Karrer), *Affinetrina sulacensis* Gerke, *A. ludwigi* (Reuss), *Ammonia beccari* (L.), *Elphidium* ex. gr. *macellum* (F. et M.). Among ostracods were determined: *Leptocythere praebos-queti* Suz., *L. collativa* Suz., *Loxoconcha eichwaldi* Livent., *Loxoconcha* sp., *Leptocythere* sp., *Cyprideis littoralis* Brady, *Mediocytherideis praeapotoica* Schweier, *Xestoleberis* sp., *Cyprinotus* ex gr. *triangularis* Kasimova. The dominate role in this assemblage belongs to foraminifers. As for ostracods, they are represented by single individuals of Upper Meotian age.

The ostracods are represented by numerous individuals in the upper part of strata: *Caspiolla acronasuta* (Livent.), *Caspiocypris candida* (Livent.), *Cypria tocoriescui* Hanganu, *Cyprinotus* ex. gr. *triangularis* Kasimova, *Pontoniella acuminata* (Zal.), *P. loczyi* (Zal.), *Leptocythere microlata* (Livent.), *L. praebosqueti* Suz., *L. goitensis* Suz., *L. praebacuana* Livent., *L. bosqueti* (Livent.), *L. collativa* Suz., *L. pontica* Suz., *Loxoconcha eichwaldi* Livent., *L. valiente* Stanceva, *L. ponticus* Agal., *Leptocythere* sp., *Cyprideis littoralis* Brady, *C. punctillata* (Brady), *C.* ex. gr. *torosa* (Jones), *Mediocytherideis praeapotoica* Schweier. Foraminifers are represented by numerous indi-viduals of two species: *Cycloforina* aff. *gracilis* Karrer and *Elphidium* ex. gr. *macellum* (F. et M.). These species were passed from the Meotian, but morphologically were changed.

In rich assemblage of Ostracods the following group of species can be distinguished:

1. The species common with those of Upper Meotian:

Leptocythere praebosqueti Suz.,

L. collativa Suz.,

Loxoconcha eichwaldi Livent.

Cyprideis littoralis Brady.

Mediocytherideis praeapotoica Schweier.

Cyprinotus ex. gr. *triangularis* Kasimova.

2. The species common with those from the Upper Meotian and Pontian deposits of Dacian basin: *Caspiolla acronasuta* (Livent.) and *Caspiocypris candida* (Livent.). But in the Black Sea-Caspian basins these species are presented only in Pontian together with:

Leptocythere goitensis Suz.,

L. pontica Suz.,

Loxococoncha ponticus Agal.

3. The species migrated from Pannonian and Dacian basins in Pontian time:

Cypria tocoriescui Hanganu.

Leptocythere microlata (Livent.)

L. praebacuana Livent.

Loxococoncha valiente Stanceva.

4. Pontian species from Paratethys basins:

Pontoniella acuminata (Zal.)

The mixed Upper Meotian - Pontian composition of given above assemblages indicates its Eupatorian Age.

So, judging from the composition of microfaunal assemblages of the Upper Meotian and Pontian between these two stretches of Neogene, the succession of fauna took place in both regions, in the Western Georgia and in Crimea. The common species for foraminifers are: *Quinqueloculina seminulum maeotica*, *Q. aff. pontica*, *Cycloforina gracilis*, *Elphidium macellum*. The number of ostracods is much numerous: *Caspiolla acronasuta*, *Cypria tocorriencui*, *Pontoniella acuminata*, *P. loczyi*, *Leptocythere goitensis*, *L. collativa*, *L. praebacuana*, *L. pontica*, *L. microlata*, *Loxococoncha eichwaldi*, *Cyprideis littoralis*, *C. punctillata*. In this list are given both, the forms passed from Upper Meotian and properly Pontian species, which first appeared in Early Pontian. Also the species characteristic for the Black Sea - Caspian and Pannonian - Dacian basins are given here. This makes easier the correlation of Pontian deposits of whole Eastern Paratethys.

Our investigations confirm the opinion of Davitashvili (1937, p. 580) about similarity of biological conditions of Upper Meotian and Eupatorian basins. Judging from the history of development of Meotian and Early Pontian foraminifers and ostracods (Djanelidze et al., 1985; Maissuradze, 1988) it is possible to conclude, that gradual deterioration of biological conditions promoted the disappearance of foraminifers in Pliocene basins of Paratethys. Their extinction began in the Late Meotian and finished in the Middle Pontian. The decrease of salinity was the main factor that influenced this process. The composition of brackish and freshwater mollusks distributed during these epochs and also the abundance of ostracods characteristic for freshwater basins indicates the above fact (Davitashvili, 1933, 1937; Ebersin, 1949, 1967; Taktakishvili, 1978; Suladze, 1984; Imnadze, 1974; Djanelidze et al., Popkhadze 1978; Neveeskaya et al., 2003; Maisuradze, Koiava, 2011). The salinity of water in basins of the Late Meotian and Pontian is determined as 5 ‰, that was pernicious for foraminifers, but favorable for ostracods, which in Pliocene became the dominant group of fossil microorganisms.

The palynological analysis

The Lower Pontian is widely distributed on whole territory of Western Georgia, but only in three localities (on the Atapi and Zana rivers and near village Bia) the Novorossian substage is represented by a full series of deposits. In all other sections the Eupatorian is absent and the Lower Pontian begins with the Odessian horizon (Chelidze 1974; Shengelia, 1976; Taktakishvili, 1984).

The palynological analysis samples from the Atapi and Zana deposits revealed that the changes in pollen assemblages at the boundary of the Miocene and Pliocene were similar in both sites (Shatilova et al., 2011).

In the beginning of the Late Meotian the territory of Western Georgia was covered with rich forest vegetation, distributed on different levels of mountain relief. Middle and lower mountain belts were covered with polydominant forest, which were composed of subtropical and warm-temperate conifers and broad-leaved trees: Podocarpus, Dacrydium, Cedrus, Keteleeria, Cathaya, Taxodiaceae, some species of *Carya*, *Quercus*, *Fagus*, *Castanea*, *Juglans*, *Platanus*, *Nyssa* and the numerous genera of family Hamamelidaceae. The forest understory consisted of subtropical ferns such as *Dicksonia*, *Gleichenia*, *Anemia*, *Polypodium*, *Pteris*.

The beginning of the Late Meotian can be considered as the climatic optimum. The decreasing role of dark-conifers and increase of pine forests was brought on by abrupt climatic changes in Early Pontian – Eupatorian time (fig.1,2).

Fig. 1. Palynological diagram of Meotian and Pontian deposits of section Atapi

Fig. 2. Palynological diagram of Meotian and Pontian deposits of section Zana

The pollen assemblages of Eupatorian show the transition from rich and diverse pollen flora of the Meotian to poor assemblages with predominance of pine. The changes in composition of vegetation, probably, were connected with decrease of humidity, phenomenon, which at the end of the Miocene embraced whole Southern part of Russian Plain (Shchekina, 1979). In Odessian the pine was replaced by dark-conifer communi-

ties, occupying almost all altitude. This suggest that after the Eupatorian the rise of humidity and decrease in temperature took place.

After the Odessian the climate again became warm and humid, especially during the Middle part of Portaferian, when the polydominant forest stabilized. It was probably during this climatic optimum that the Kodorian flora accumulated.

The Pontian pollen assemblages we compared with those from synchronous deposits of Northern part of Black Sea coast. In both regions the rhythmic changes of epochs with different climates can be traced. However in the Western Georgia the frequency and amplitudes of these changes were weaker. The main differences between the northern Black Sea coast and Western Georgia was in terms of humidity. In the north, the Pontian was a time of declining temperatures and xerophytisation (Ananova, 1974), while in Colchis precipitation increased side by side with gradually lowering of temperatures.

Conclision

On the basis of given above data it is possible to conclude, that in the history of marine microfauna the Eupatorian was the turning-point. After Eupatorian nearly fully disappeared the foraminifers, which prevailed in the basins of Eastern Paratethys during the whole Miocene and the predominate position was occupied by ostracods.

Significant changes in composition of macrofauna were also connected with the beginning of Eupatorian. In the Black Sea - Caspian region in this time first appeared genera: *Didacna*, *Monodacna* and *Prosodacna*.

On the territory of Western Georgia the Eupatorian was the turning- point also in history of climate and vegetation, after which their dynamics was changed. During the whole Pliocene the gradually increasing of frequency and amplitudes of climatic fluctuations was proceeded. This process received the highest degree of development in the Pleistocene.

So, in Eastern part of the Black Sea region the Eupatorian horizon can be considered as the level, after which the Miocene stage of development of marine and terrestrial biocenosis was changed by Pliocene one.

პალეობიოლოგია

შავი ზღვის რეგიონის გვიანმოტური და ადრეპონტური ნალექების მიკროპალეონტოლოგიური შესწავლის შედეგები

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რეზიუმე

სტატიაში მოცემულია გვიანმოტური და ადრეპონტური ნალექების მიკროფაუნისა (ფორამინიფერები, ოსტრაკოდები) და პალინომორფების შესწავლის შედეგები. გამოყენებულია აგრეთვე ლიტერატურული მონაცემები მოლუსკური ფაუნის შესახებ. მიკროფაუნისტური მასალა შეგროვილია დასავლეთ საქართველოში და ყირიმში საკვლევი ნალექების ჭრილებიდან. დასავლეთ საქართველოში აღწერილია ორი ჭრილი - მდ. ატაპის ხეობაში და სოფ. ბიას მიდამოებში, ხოლო ყირიმში სტრატოტიპული ჭრილის გამოსავლები ქ. ევპატორიის მახლობლად. პალინოლოგიური მასალა შეგროვილია ორი ჭრილიდან - მდ. მდ. ატაპის და ხანას ხეობებში.

შესწავლილ ჭრილებში გამოყოფილია ფაუნისტურად დათარიღებული გვიანმოტური და ადრეპონტური (ევპატორიული, ოდესური) ნალექები, მათი უხარვეზო თანდათანობითი, მდორე, გადასვლით. ფაუნისტური კომპლექსების შემადგენლობა და მათი ხასიათი ცალკეული პონტური სახეობების მეოტურ წინაპრებთან მემკვიდრეობითობას აჩვენებს.

გვიანმოტურ აუზში ეკოლოგიური პირობების გაუარესებამ (განმარილიანება) ფორამინიფერების თანდათანობითი გაღარიბებისა და შუაპონტურის დასაწყისისთვის მათი ამოწყდომის მთავარი მიზეზი გახდა. იმ დროს როდესაც შექმნილი ბიონომიური პირობები ოსტრაკოდებისათვის იმდენად ოპტიმალური აღმოჩნდა, რომ მათ გაფურჩქნას ანუ ახალი გვარებისა და სახეობების გაჩენას შეუწყო ხელი. მსგავსი პროცესი გრძელდებოდა მთელი პლიოცენის განმავლობაში.

მიკროფაუნის განვითარების ისტორია გვიანმოტური და ადრეპონტური საუკუნეების მიჯნაზე არსებულ მკვეთრ გარდატეხას აჩვენებს, რაც ჩვენი აზრით მიოცენური ეპოქის დასასრულად და პლიოცენურის დასაწყისად უნდა მივიჩნიოთ.

იგივე ითქმის ხმელეთის ფლორის ისტორიის შესახებაც. ევპატორიულის შემდეგ გვიანმოტურ ეპოქის შედარებით სტაბილური კლიმატური პირობები შეიცვალა ნაკლებად სტაბილური პლიოცენური ეპოქისათვის დამახასიათებელი კლიმატით.

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